

CodeCombat

Developed by: CodeCombat Inc.

Article contributed by: Jonathan Sierks

Keywords

Algorithms, C++, Computer Science, Data Structures, JavaScript, Mathematics, Programming, Python, Software Development, Technology

Introduction

CodeCombat is a digital learning game for teaching software programming concepts and languages, first released by CodeCombat Inc. in 2013. The game teaches programming languages such as Python, JavaScript, C++, Java, and Lua, as well as the fundamentals of computer science. In CodeCombat, the player character is controlled through various levels by writing code. Progress in learning is supported by unlocking new items, which gives players direct feedback. By completing levels, the character can rise in rank, with learning playing a central role, as new levels and worlds can only be unlocked by acquiring new skills.

Facts

Release date:	First released in 2013, continuously updated
Developer:	CodeCombat Inc.
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Scalable
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	A few minutes per level up to several hours per module; about 400 levels in total.
Languages:	Available in over 50 languages, including English, German, and Spanish
Environment:	Laptop or PC with internet access
Material:	All required materials are provided online; a subscription grants access to additional content
Price:	Free, subscription available

Resonance & Criticism

CodeCombat received a significant distinction when the College Board recommended it for the AP Computer Science Principles course during the 2019–2020 school year, an introductory college-level computer science course. The College Board, which also administers and develops the Scholastic Assessment Test (SAT), the U.S. college entrance exam, rarely issues such endorsements. In 2024, CodeCombat Inc. reported more than 20 million users.

Game Principle & Process

Figure 1. In-game programming interface of CodeCombat (CodeCombat Inc.), showing a player controlling a character by writing code. Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

The core game principle is that players solve programming tasks by writing code that controls a hero's actions (see Figure 1). This character must defeat enemies, solve puzzles, and overcome obstacles — all by having players enter the correct lines of code into a text box. The game mechanics are therefore closely linked to programming: every character action depends directly on the player's code.

At the beginning, simple programming concepts are introduced, while the tasks become increasingly complex as the game progresses. Players must guide their hero to specific locations, attack enemies, or collect items. Over time, more advanced concepts such as loops, conditionals, functions, and data structures must be learned and applied. If a level is not completed successfully, players can analyze and correct their code, which is a central part of the learning process. This immediate feedback and the opportunity to fix errors encourage problem-solving skills.

In addition to the single-player mode, CodeCombat also offers a multiplayer mode in which players compete against each other. Here, they program their characters to fight in an arena. The player with the best code wins the match.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

CodeCombat aims to teach students, especially beginners, fundamental programming skills and to make advanced concepts such as loops, conditionals, algorithms, Boolean logic, and

nested conditions more accessible. A key aspect of CodeCombat is the stimulating and motivating learning environment (see Karram, 2021), which is created through the game and facilitates programming learning.

In addition, CodeCombat offers specialized curricula for educational institutions that systematically teach programming skills. Teachers can monitor their students' progress and guide them through tailored lessons.

Overall, CodeCombat skillfully combines elements of an adventure game with the teaching of programming knowledge. Through the direct connection between the written code and the game's visible actions, the abstract subject of programming becomes more concrete and motivating. Players gradually develop their skills and are encouraged by the reward system and the increasing difficulty to deepen their programming knowledge.

Using CodeCombat is straightforward for teachers. A free account can be created on the platform to start working with the basic functions immediately. Access to extended features and learning materials via a subscription may be helpful, but it is not strictly necessary. The platform offers extensive resources and guides that help users get started, keeping preparation time manageable.

Effectiveness

A 2021 study by Kroustalli & Xinogalos examined the effectiveness of CodeCombat as a learning tool for teaching programming. The sample consisted of 59 lower-secondary students, and was divided into an experimental (CodeCombat) and a control (traditional teaching) group. Knowledge development was measured using pre- and post-tests. The results suggest that the experimental group performed better in the post-test than the control group, although the difference was not statistically significant. Further studies are needed to determine whether and to what extent CodeCombat provides a statistically significant improvement over traditional methods — although studies such as Kroustalli & Xinogalos (2021) suggest that positive effects may indeed be demonstrable.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

One limitation is that CodeCombat does not offer specific adaptations for learners with disabilities. Additionally, individual levels cannot be skipped, which may frustrate players who already have basic programming experience.

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

Sources

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